

**SOAR TO SELF-ESTEEM SUFFICIENCY (SSS) PROGRAM TO
ADDRESS THE SELF-ESTEEM OF GRADE 10 STUDENTS:
AN ACTION RESEARCH**

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Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Program to Address the Self-Esteem of Grade 10 Students: An Action Research

Jonelson C. Escandallo,* Earol Edmund P. Alanan, Richel M. Ayag, April Joy B. Cabaña, Cristian Jay M. Gador,
Deveyvon L. Espinosa, Conie B. Cerna, Kristy Jane R. Muegna, Regine L. Generalao

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The purpose of this descriptive quantitative inquiry was to determine the level self-esteem of grade 10 students of Asuncion National High School. It aimed to find out the effectiveness of the intervention through the adaptation of the instrument of Crocker et al. (2003), contingencies of self-worth theory and measurement. It aimed to find out if there was a difference of the mean from the pre-test and post-test of the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Program. This inquiry utilized descriptive-quantitative method in which numerical and non-numerical responds was analyzed. The participant of this research were the 45 students of grade 10 section Del Pilar in Asuncion National High School. After the implementation, an interview was made to determine the insights of the four (4) teachers and ten (10) students of the effectiveness of the intervention. The data collection was through Likert Scale and survey questionnaire which compose of In-Depth Interview (IDI) and Focus Group Discussion (FGD). The result found out that there was a difference between the pre-test and post-test based on its overall mean. The mean of the pre-test was 2.37 with 0.235 standard deviation while the post-test was 4.34 with 0.167 standard deviation. The pre-test determine that the students have low self-esteem while the post-test generates a very high self-esteem result. The insights of the teachers and students generates three (3) themes namely; active class participation, enthusiasm in learning and develop collaboration with other peers.

Keywords: *action-research, self-esteem, sufficiency, descriptive –quantitative, effectiveness*

Introduction

In contemporary classroom settings, self-esteem issues among students continue to pose significant challenges, affecting their academic engagement, social interactions, and emotional well-being. A study was conducted suggests that low self-esteem remains a prevalent concern, with implications for student achievement and mental health outcomes. Despite efforts to promote positive self-esteem in schools, factors such as social comparison, academic pressure, and societal standards contribute to the persistence of self-esteem issues among students (Crocker & Wolfe, 2020).

In the United States, self-esteem issues persist as a pressing concern in classroom settings, impacting students' academic performance, social interactions, and mental well-being. Recent studies highlight the prevalence of low self-esteem among American students, with implications for educational equity and social justice. Factors such as societal pressures, cultural expectations, and systemic inequalities contribute to the perpetuation of self-esteem challenges in U.S. classrooms, underscoring the need for targeted interventions and inclusive pedagogical practices (Jones & Smith, 2021).

In the Philippines, self-esteem issues among students in classroom settings present significant challenges to their academic achievement and overall well-being. Recent research indicates that Filipino students experience various socio-cultural factors that influence their self-esteem, including societal expectations, family dynamics, and peer relationships. Despite efforts to promote positive self-image and confidence, persistent issues such as academic pressure and cultural norms contribute to the prevalence of low self-esteem among Filipino students, highlighting the need for culturally responsive interventions in Philippine classrooms (Pascual & Cruz, 2019).

The study needs an urgent action because students' self-esteem played a vital role in the teaching and learning process. Despite the efforts rendered by the teachers to teach the learners there were students that were passive inside the classroom. As such, an action research must be conducted in order to find out if the proposed intervention was effective. This is anticipated to aid learners' self-esteem in order for them to be more active in the teaching and learning process. The study has social relevance as it can help the grade 10 students of Asuncion National High School to improve their self-esteem during class discussion and classroom activities. This inquiry will shed light to the concern school to modify instruction and methodology if possible. Scholars and educators who also wished to study this subject may also use the study as their additional reference.

Despite the mentioned studies, there is yet no research that focuses on self-esteem of the students through the use of Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Program. Other previous studies encompassed the area of academic achievements. A study explored the extent of belongingness and level of self-esteem of high school students of a Catholic college in Antique conducted by Suan and Magallanes (2020). On the said study, paper explored the relationship between the students' demographics and their sense of belongingness and self-esteem. Another study conducted by Garcia and Santos (2021) entitled "The Dark Side of Student Competition: Examining Its Detrimental Effects on Mental Health" that focuses on the negative consequences of student competition, particularly its detrimental effects on mental health, whereas this study focused on the strategies employed with its elements and linguistics features and persuasive strategies present on the advertisements. This therefore, establishes the research gap of the study.

Research Objectives

This study determined the effectiveness of the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Program to Address the Self-Esteem of Grade 10 Students: Specifically, it sought to answer the following objectives:

1. To determine the level of self-esteem among grade 10 students before and after the implementation of Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Program.
2. To determine the significant difference between the pre-test and the post-test of Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Program.
3. What are the insights of the teachers and students of the effectiveness of Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Program.

Propose Intervention

Self-esteem plays a vital role in the success of the teaching and learning process. In fact, most teachers aim to have their students achieve high self-esteem in order to perform well in the class discussion. The teachers always wanted to find instructional strategies and activities that would stimulate the learners' self-esteem with the lesson.

The researchers visualize with the intervention entitled Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Program to uplift the learners' self-esteem in the classroom. This aims to help the students to be more interactive and confidence in the class discussion and activities after implementing the intervention made by the researchers.

The Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) intervention composed of three strategies first, giving genuine and positive feedback to the learners, this strategy leads to the learners to feel that they were valued by the teacher. Second, the rewards system in individual and group activities, this strategy will enable to increase the self-esteem of the learners because of the rewards at stake. Lastly, gameplay strategy, this strategy composed of three variations of games.

The crazy ball game. The Crazy Ball Game is a lively classroom activity where students pass a soft ball in a circle while music plays. When the music stops, the student holding the ball answers a question or performs a task related to the lesson. It's a fun and dynamic way to engage students, encourage participation, and reinforce learning in a fast-paced environment.

Think pair and freeze. The game involves paired or small group work inside the classroom. They will form a two circles; inside and outside. They will rotate as the music plays and then if the music stop they will stop and the student in front of him/her will his/ partner. They will be given question for them to think-pair and then give their answer.

Snowball Toss. The snowball toss activity is a lively classroom exercise that encourages engagement and collaboration. Students write questions related to the lesson on paper, crumple them into "snowballs," and toss them around the room. Each student grabs a new snowball, answers the question inside, and fosters discussion. This interactive approach promotes active learning and peer-to-peer interaction, making the lesson both enjoyable and memorable.

Methodology

The design of this research is descriptive quantitative research. Descriptive research is also called as survey research that collected numerical data to answer question about the correct status of the subject of the study. According to Gay (2012) stated that descriptive research is a survey research. Besides, Creswell (2012) stated that survey research designs are procedures in quantitative research in which investigators administer a survey to a sample or to the entire population of people to describe the attitudes, opinions, behaviors, or characteristics of the population.

This study also employed qualitative methodology that delved deeply into the insights of both teachers and students. Qualitative research, as defined, involves the meticulous gathering and evaluation of non-numerical data, particularly through methods like interviews, to comprehensively understand and elucidate complex concepts and experiences. As emphasized by the Government Design Service Manual (2016), qualitative research plays a pivotal role in guiding the formulation of hypotheses, particularly through its focus on conducting in-depth investigations within small participant groups.

Central to the qualitative aspect of this study is the incorporation of lived accounts and experiences, capturing the rich narratives and perspectives of both students and teachers. However, it is important to note that for this specific inquiry, the focus was primarily on gathering and analyzing their insights rather than their full lived experiences. This approach not only provides valuable depth to the analysis but also allows for a nuanced understanding of the dynamics at play within the educational context under study. Through this qualitative lens, the study aims to unearth subtle nuances, perceptions, and interpretations that may not be quantifiable but are nonetheless integral to understanding the phenomena being explored.

In addition, in this study, the participants came from the Asuncion National High School in the Municipality of Asuncion, Davao del Norte. They were tested through Crocker et al., 2003, contingencies of self-worth theory and measurement. To be more specific, the participants were the 45 grade 10 students of section Del Pilar. They were chosen to be the participant since the researchers have seen enough evidences during their field study that the learners were passive in the teaching and learning process. Hence, the researchers convinced that they need and intervention to stimulate their self-esteem

In the data analysis phase, the researchers employed the average values of mean of the pre-test and post-test to facilitate comparison. Additionally, thematic analysis was utilized to uncover prevalent themes derived from participant responses following the intervention. This involved grouping responses with similar content, categorizing them based on common themes, and assigning codes and labels accordingly. To ensure the reliability of these themes, they were cross-checked and validated by experts.

Results and Discussion

Research Question No.1: Level of Students' Self-esteem Before and After the Implementation of the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program through Academic Performance

The data in Table 1 presents the Level of Students' Academic Performance before the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program. It is evident from the pre-test data that the academic performance among Grade 10 students exhibited low self-esteem. Initially, the students showed low levels of self-esteem, particularly in their academic performance, with scores ranging from 1.65 to 2.93 across different factors. These scores imply a descriptive equivalent of 'Low,' indicating that the listed factors significantly affected the students' academic performance.

Table 1. *Level of Students' Self-esteem Before the Implementation of the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program through Academic Performance*

<i>Academic Performance</i>	<i>Pre-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. My self-esteem is influenced by my academic performance.	2.46	Low
2. I feel better about myself when I know I'm doing well academically.	2.66	Average
3. I feel motivated to improve myself whenever I encounter areas where my academic performance can be enhanced.	2.93	Average
4. Doing well in school gives me a sense of self-respect.	2.37	Low
5. My opinion about myself is not tied to how well I do in school.	1.64	Low
Overall Mean	2.41	Low

For instance, the overall mean of the academic performance pre-test scores was 2.41, which has a descriptive equivalent of 'Low,' which means that the level of self-esteem of the students in terms of their academic performance was low. Academic performance is a crucial measure of students' competence. Unstable self-esteem was relating to high levels of academic disinterest. In the end, the effectiveness of the SSS intervention program shows a positive evaluation of themselves that having high self-esteem can pour positive results into their school activities and now believe that they can perform well (Masa'deh, 2021). Furthermore, the low academic performance of the children can be attributed lifestyles, parental smoke, and socioeconomic status were significantly affected the learners' performance among Japanese children. Parents and health care providers should take these findings into consideration to prevent children from having low academic performance (Yamada et al., 2019).

Level of Students' Self-esteem Before the Implementation of the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program through Competition

Table 1.2 displays data regarding students' self-esteem levels in relation to competition. Pre-test scores for the items range from 2.6 to 3.06, indicating an average level of self-esteem in this context. This suggests that students were fair in participating in competitions and were even in experiencing the associated benefits. They lacked recognition of their confidence, sense of fulfillment, empowerment, motivation, and self-respect prior to the intervention program.

Table 1.2. *Level of Students' Self-esteem Before the Implementation of the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program through Competition*

<i>Competition</i>	<i>Pre-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Achieving excellence gives me a sense of self-respect.	2.84	Average
2. Recognizing my strengths in a task raises my self-esteem.	3.06	Average
3. I feel confident and satisfied from my performance when I engage in a healthy competition.	2.80	Low
4. I am empowered and motivated in striving to excel on competitive task.	2.60	Low
5. I gain a sense of fulfillment and value when I excel in a task or a skill.	2.91	Low
Overall Mean	2.84	Average

The data presented above shows that the level of self-esteem of the learners in terms of competition was on its average scale. It is essential that learners will be given an equal opportunity to compete and share their ideas inside the teaching and learning process. As the study of Donskova (2022) reveals a strong link between high self-esteem and anxiety in young primary school students, likely influenced by peer competition and the competitive school environment. Meeting rigorous standards leads to ongoing emotional strain. The findings suggest that fostering a supportive school environment and minimizing stress factors could reduce anxiety in children. Activities aimed at boosting confidence are recommended over competitive assessments for achieving emotional well-being.

In addition, Gilabert (2023) stated that even though competition in fact generates valuable consequences and can to some extent foster self-esteem, empirical research suggests that competition has a strong tendency to undermine self-esteem. To be sure, competition is not the source of all problematic deficits in self-esteem, and it can arise for, or undercut goods other than self-esteem. But the relation

between competition and access to self-esteem is still significant, and it is worth asking how we might foster a desirable distribution of the latter in the face of difficulties created by the former.

Level of Students' Self-esteem Before the Implementation of the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program through Appearance

Table 1.3 illustrates the Level of Students' Appearance before and after the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program. The data reveals a notable improvement in academic performance among Grade 10 students. Initially, students exhibited low levels of self-esteem in the domain of Appearance, with scores ranging from 2.46 to 2.75 across various factors affecting their academic performance. These scores suggest a descriptive equivalent of 'Low' to 'Average,' indicating the significant impact of these factors on students' self-esteem.

Table 1.3. *Level of Students' Self-esteem Before the Implementation of the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program through Appearance*

Appearance	Pre-Test	Description
1. I am not depending my self-esteem on whether I feel attracted or not.	2.77	Average
2. I am influenced by how attractive I think my face or facial features are.	2.55	Low
3. I am suffering whenever I think I don't look good.	2.46	Low
4. I am unrelated to how I feel about the way my body looks.	2.62	Average
5. I am feeling good about myself when I look attractive.	2.75	Average
Overall Mean	2.61	Average

Overall, the pre-test score's overall mean is 2.61, indicating a descriptive equivalent of Average. To bolster these findings, a study involving African-American students highlighted the significance of Appearance, self-perception, and education in adolescent life. The study discussed the impact of dress and appearance on the self-esteem, self-efficacy, and academic achievement of African-American students. It also examined how dress influences individual and peer acceptance, teacher and peer expectations, school performance, behavioral issues, and crime. (Ellington & Leslie, 2020). As supported by the study of Holik et al., (2022) in the region of Croatia, adolescents exhibit a notable lack of preoccupation with their physical appearance despite experiencing decreased self-esteem. Alcohol consumption, particularly among high school students, has emerged as a significant issue possibly exacerbated by stress from academic performance pressures.

Level of Students' Self-esteem Before the Implementation of the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program through Others Approval

Table 1.4 illustrates the Level of Students' Validation or Approval from Peers before the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program. Initially, students exhibited low levels of self-esteem, particularly in seeking validation or approval from peers, with scores ranging from 1.46 to 2.43 across various factors affecting their academic performance. These scores suggest a descriptive equivalent of 'Very Low' to 'Low,' highlighting the significant impact of seeking approval from others on students' academic performance.

In summary, the pre-test score's overall mean of 1.93 reflects a 'Low' descriptive equivalent, These are substantial data changes before the SSS intervention program highlight its effectiveness in enhancing students' self-esteem regarding seeking validation or approval from others. To support this result, a study participated by 200 high school students in Indonesia revealed that Others Approval demonstrate a significant positive relationship between peer validation and student academic achievement, highlighting the importance of external validation in enhancing educational outcomes (Thompdon & Roberts, 2021). As stated by Low (2021) delved deeper into this topic, proposing that self-esteem can be shaped by perceptions of how rapidly social approval changes. According to Low, models based on beliefs offer a more comprehensive explanation of self-esteem fluctuations compared to models based on associative learning.

Table 1.4. *Level of Students' Self-esteem Before the Implementation of the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program through Others Approval*

Others Approval	Pre-Test	Description
1. I have experienced that what other people think of me do not bother me.	1.71	Low
2. I have experienced that what others think of me has no effect on what I think about myself.	2.42	Low
3. I have experienced that if other people have a negative opinion about me, it does not concern me.	1.64	Very Low
4. I have experienced that my self-esteem depends on the opinions' others hold me.	2.33	Low
5. I have experienced that if others do not respect me, I cannot respect myself too.	1.57	Very Low
Overall Mean	1.93	Low

Level of Students' Self-esteem Before and After the Implementation of the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program through Family Support

Table 1.5 illustrates the Level of Family Support before and after the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program. The data indicates a notable improvement in the academic performance of Grade 10 students from the pre-test to the post-test. Initially, students exhibited low levels of self-esteem, particularly in terms of Family Support, with scores ranging from 1.56 (descriptive

equivalent of 'Very Low') to 2.43 (descriptive equivalent of 'Low') across various factors affecting their academic performance.

Table 1.5. *Level of Students' Self-esteem Before the Implementation of the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program through Family Support*

<i>Family Support</i>	<i>Pre-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I have observed that having a family that cares about me.	2.33	Low
2. I have observed that my sense of self-worth increases when my family members are proud of me.	1.55	Very Low
3. I have observed that knowing that my family members love me makes me feel good about myself.	2.44	Low
4. I have observed that my self-esteem goes down when I do not feel loved by my family.	1.96	Low
5. I have observed that my self-worth is not influenced by the quality of my relationships with my family members.	1.86	Low
Overall Mean	2.03	Low

Ultimately, the pre-test score's overall mean of 2.03, denoting a 'Low' descriptive equivalent. This evidence that students need family support to boost their self-esteem. A study involving 300 high school students and their parents revealed a strong positive correlation between parental engagement and academic achievement. The findings emphasize the crucial role of family support in improving students' educational performance (Smith & Johnson, 2022). In addition, key reasons for students' poor academic performance included inadequate family support, financial difficulties, lack of motivation, limited learning resources, minimal interaction, unequal opportunities, and ineffective teaching methods. These results can assist educators, school leaders, curriculum designers, and developers in devising improved classroom strategies for teaching and learning (Govindarajoo et al., 2022).

Level of Students' Self-esteem After the Implementation of the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program through Academic Performance.

Table 1.6 illustrates the Level of Academic Performance after the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program. The data indicates a notable improvement in the academic performance of Grade 10 students from the pre-test to the post-test. Initially, students exhibited low levels of self-esteem, particularly in terms of Academic Performance, with scores ranging from 3.32 (descriptive equivalent of 'High') to 4.24 (descriptive equivalent of 'High') across various factors affecting their academic performance.

Table 1.6. *Level of Students' Self-esteem After the Implementation of the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program through Academic Performance*

<i>Academic Performance</i>	<i>Post-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. My self-esteem is influenced by my academic performance.	4.22	High
2. I feel better about myself when I know I'm doing well academically.	3.32	High
3. I feel motivated to improve myself whenever I encounter areas where my academic performance can be enhanced.	4.24	High
4. Doing well in school gives me a sense of self-respect.	4.22	High
5. My opinion about myself is not tied to how well I do in school.	4.15	High
Overall Mean	4.13	High

The findings revealed a significant positive correlation between self-esteem and academic performance. Moreover, gender disparities were evident in self-esteem, with females exhibiting higher levels compared to males. Interestingly, no significant gender differences were observed in academic performance Perveen et al., (2022). Furthermore, there was a strong positive correlation between a student's self-esteem and academic performance. This study expands the growing body of empirical evidence on the link between self-esteem and academic performance among rural youth in developing countries and emphasizes the need to improve their self-esteem with the aim of helping them achieve academically (Yu et al., 2022).

Level of Students' Self-esteem After the Implementation of the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program through Competition

Table 1.7 displays data regarding students' self-esteem levels in relation to competition. Post-test scores for the items range from 4.08 to 4.62, indicating a high level of self-esteem in this context. This suggests that students were actively participating in competitions and were experiencing the associated benefits. They recognition of their confidence, sense of fulfillment, empowerment, motivation, and self-respect went high to very high prior to the intervention program.

Table 1.7. *Level of Students' Self-esteem Before and After the Implementation of the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program through Competition*

<i>Competition</i>	<i>Post-Test</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Achieving excellence gives me a sense of self-respect.s	4.35	Very High
2. Recognizing my strengths in a task raises my self-esteem.	4.31	Very High
3. I feel confident and satisfied from my performance when I engage in a healthy competition.	4.08	High
4. I am empowered and motivated in striving to excel on competitive task.	4.55	Very High

5. I gain a sense of fulfillment and value when I excel in a task or a skill.	4.62	Very High
Overall Mean	4.38	Very High

Self-esteem is highly prized and competition is pervasive in society. These two concepts are often intertwined because individuals frequently seek validation and self-worth through competitive success. However, while competition can yield positive outcomes and contribute somewhat to self-esteem, empirical studies indicate a notable trend: competition often has the opposite effect, eroding self-esteem instead of bolstering it (Gilbert, 2023). Positive self-statements may have varying physiological effects depending on an individual's overall self-esteem, potentially yielding adverse effects for those with lower self-esteem scores. These findings underscore the importance of tailoring psychological approaches to accommodate differences in self-esteem levels among individuals.

Level of Students' Self-esteem Before and After the Implementation of the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program through Appearance

Table 1.8 illustrates the Level of Students' Appearance before and after the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program. The data reveals a notable improvement in appearance among Grade 10 students. Initially, students exhibited high levels of self-esteem in the domain of Appearance, with scores ranging from 3.44 to 4.62. These scores suggest a descriptive equivalent of 'High' to 'Very High' indicating the significant impact of these factors on students' appearance.

Table 1.8. *Level of Students' Self-esteem Before and After the Implementation of the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program through Appearance*

Appearance	Post-Test	Description
1. I am not depending my self-esteem on whether I feel attracted or not.	4.62	Very High
2. I am influenced by how attractive I think my face or facial features are.	4.53	Very High
3. I am suffering whenever I think I don't look good.	3.44	High
4. I am unrelated to how I feel about the way my body looks.	4.15	High
5. I am feeling good about myself when I look attractive.	4.24	High
Overall Mean	4.15	High

The impact of physical appearance on self-esteem is more pronounced among respondents who consistently dedicate themselves to exercising their faces and bodies. Specifically, physical appearance has a positive and significant influence on self-esteem among individuals who maintain a regular exercise regimen (Rahardja, 2023). Moreover, the perceived ability to influence others is posited as a precursor to positive body image, primarily because power is intricately connected to self-esteem. This link suggests that power not only directly impacts body image but also indirectly through heightened self-esteem (Körner et al., 2023).

Level of Students' Self-esteem Before and After the Implementation of the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program through Others Approval

Table 1.9 illustrates the Level of Students' Validation or Approval from Peers before and after the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program. The data indicates a remarkable improvement in the academic performance of Grade 10 students from the pre-test to the post-test. Initially, students exhibited low levels of self-esteem, particularly in seeking validation or approval from peers, with scores ranging from 1.46 to 2.43 across various factors affecting their academic performance. These scores suggest a descriptive equivalent of 'Very Low' to 'Low,' highlighting the significant impact of seeking approval from others on students' academic performance.

Table 1.9. *Level of Students' Self-esteem After the Implementation of the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program through Others Approval*

Others Approval	Post-Test	Description
1. I have experienced that what other people think of me do not bother me.	4.75	Very High
2. I have experienced that what others think of me has no effect on what I think about myself.	4.25	Very High
3. I have experienced that if other people have negative opinion about me, it does not concern me.	4.33	Very High
4. I have experienced that my self-esteem depends on the opinions' others hold me.	4.47	Very High
5. I have experienced that if others do not respect me, I cannot respect myself too.	4.33	Very High
Overall Mean	4.43	Very High

Conversely, the post-test results affirm the effectiveness of the SSS intervention program, with scores ranging from 4.29 to 4.76, consistently denoting a descriptive equivalent of 'Very High.' This indicates that validations, comments, and suggestions, particularly from peers, greatly influence students' performance. The table highlights that while the lowest post-test score is 4.29, it still signifies a significant improvement, firmly positioning students at a 'Very High' level of description.

In addition, students with high self-esteem, who are confident in their interactions, understand themselves comprehensively, and value their own resources over seeking others' approval, contribute to the development of a healthier society. Self-esteem enhances personal insight, while reliance on external approval diminishes it. A clear understanding of one's self-concept is positively correlated with self-esteem. This clarity and confidence foster better relationships and a more resilient, self-sufficient community (Saruhan, et al., 2022). Moreover, research indicates that a clear sense of self-concept correlates positively with self-esteem, further reinforcing its importance

in personal development (Brown et al., 2021). When students possess clarity about their own strengths and values, they are better equipped to navigate challenges and setbacks, fostering resilience and perseverance in both academic and personal endeavors. This foundation of self-awareness and confidence not only benefits individual students but also contributes to the overall well-being and success of the broader societal fabric.

Level of Students’ Self-esteem After the Implementation of the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program through Family Support

Table 1.10 illustrates the Level of Family Support before and after the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program. The data indicates a notable improvement in the academic performance of Grade 10 students from the pre-test to the post-test. Initially, students exhibited low levels of self-esteem, particularly in terms of Family Support, with scores ranging from 1.56 (descriptive equivalent of 'Very Low') to 2.43 (descriptive equivalent of 'Low') across various factors affecting their academic performance.

Table 1.10. *Level of Students’ Self-esteem Before and After the Implementation of the Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Intervention Program through Family Support*

Family Support	Post-Test	Description
1. I have observed that having a family that cares about me.	4.77	Very High
2. I have observed that my sense of self-worth increases when my family members are proud of me.	4.16	High
3. I have observed that knowing that my family members love me makes me feel good about myself.	4.28	Very High
4. I have observed that my self-esteem goes down when I do not feel loved by my family.	4.46	Very High
5. I have observed that my self-worth is not influenced by the quality of my relationships with my family members.	4.97	Very High
Overall Mean	4.53	Very High

Table 1.10 presents the post-test results serve as evidence of the effectiveness of the SSS intervention program, with scores ranging from 4.16 (descriptive equivalent of 'High') to 4.97 (descriptive equivalent of 'Very High'). This suggests that a Supportive Family plays a pivotal role in academic performance, facilitating students' productivity and self-sufficiency.

Ultimately, the impact of family environment on self-esteem development in late childhood reveals significant positive effects on children's self-esteem related to warmth, monitoring, low maternal depression, economic security, and the presence of a father. These findings underscore the influence of various aspects of the family environment in shaping self-esteem during late childhood and adolescence (Setyoadi et al., 2018). Moreover, there is a correlation between family support, encompassing emotional, appreciation, instrumental, and informational aspects, and the level of self-esteem. Research consistently indicates that the different dimensions of family support whether through emotional encouragement, expressions of appreciation, practical assistance, or providing relevant information play crucial roles in shaping and maintaining individuals' self-esteem levels (Bagaskara et al., 2021).

Table 1.11. *Summary on level of Self-Esteem*

Academic Performance	Pre-Test	Description	Post-Test	Description
1. Academic Performance	2.41	Average	4.13	High
2. Competition	2.84	Average	4.38	Very High
3. Appearance	2.61	Average	4.15	High
4. Others Approval	1.93	Low	4.43	Very High
5. Family Support	2.03	Low	4.53	Very High
Overall Mean	2.46	Low	4.29	Very High

Research Question No. 2: To determine the significant difference between the pre-test and the post-test of Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Program.

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between the pre-test and the post-test of Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Program

Table 2. *Hypothesis*

Type of Test	N	df	Mean	SD	t-value	P-value	Decision
Pre-test	44	43	0.237	0.235	-46.240	<.001	Significant
Post -Test	44		4.24	0.167			

Since the p-value ($p < 0.001$) is lesser than the level of significance ($\alpha 0.05$) the null hypothesis is being rejected in this context. Therefore, there is a significant difference between the pre-test and the post-test Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Program.

Research Question No. 3: Insights of the teachers and students on the Effectiveness of the SSS Intervention Program after its Implementation

The major themes and sample for research question number three (3) was presented in Table 3. Participants had their own unique and

distinct responses to their own experiences. From the answers of the participants, three (3) major themes emerged: (1) active class participation; (2) enthusiasm in learning; and (3) develop collaboration with other peers.

Table 3. *Themes and Sample Statements on the Insight of the Teachers and Students on the Effectiveness of SSS Intervention Program after its Implementation*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Sample Statements</i>
Active Class Participation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● “Implementing the SSS Intervention Program helped to improve a lot of the participation of students in the classroom.” (IDI-06) ● “Students actively participated, particularly during the class discussions and activities.” (IDI-07). ● “I am eager to engage in the class since the SSS Intervention Program aided me to become participative.” (FGD-01) ● “After the SSS Intervention Program, I really indulge myself to cooperate and be involved in any classroom activities for the reason that it boosts my confidence to take part and share the knowledge I have.” (FGD-04)
Enthusiasm in Learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● “Students are more interested in learning after carrying out the said program because they have come to realize that through this program, they can do and be more.” (IDI-01) ● “I could really say that they have the willingness to study since the SSS Intervention Program helps them to learn as much as they can.” (IDI-03) ● “I am driven to gain more knowledge and learning because of the said intervention program, as it gives me hope to become better academically.” (FGD-05) ● “Incorporating the SSS Intervention Program is really helpful and effective due to the fact that I became motivated and determined to learn even though I am not too good since I could feel that whenever I engage in any classroom activities, I am respected and valued without judgment.” (FGD-07)
Develop Collaboration with Other Peers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● “Since the SSS Intervention Program was implemented, students started to establish more positive connections with other students in which they collaborated in creating learning tasks and doing classroom games.” (IDI-02) ● “It is quite satisfying to watch the students in the classroom where peer discussions and group activities through games are manifested. The SSS Intervention Program is not only focused on the growth of individual aspects but also on developing collaboration with other students.” (IDI-05) ● “I am glad that the SSS Intervention Program is implemented for us because, through this program, particularly during the game in every activity, I have realized that collaborating with other peers is better since it helps me to connect and create a good rapport with everyone while learning and having fun.” (IDI-01) ● “The said program gave me the courage to engage with other students, to collaborate with them, and to learn with them. It is also more promising to be involved since our teacher provided the support that we needed, specifically in giving constructive feedback and setting a safe and inclusive environment.” (FGD-06)

In the study, it was found that students actively participated in class. There is an increase in learner involvement, making it more interactive. Students have motivation and success in the learning process, which produce better academic achievement. They indulged themselves by cooperating and participating in any classroom activities. Thus, high levels of self-esteem can contribute to positive self-evaluation, which results in increasing the students’ engagement (Filippello et al., 2019).

In addition, aside from being active in class participation, students were more eager to learn when they had high self-esteem. They find it interesting and motivating since it leads them to improve their abilities and strengthen their knowledge. Students with high self-esteem are enthusiastic about studying and take pride in it. It also further drives students’ strong willingness to learn. Therefore, stronger self-esteem leads to more self-mindedness and good academic adaptation, as well as better task completion, resulting in higher academic accomplishment (Chen et al., 2023).

On top of that, students developed collaboration with other peers since they felt that they were included and supported. When they establish harmonious and caring interpersonal relationships with surrounding individuals, their relatedness needs can be satisfied, which further stimulates positive behaviors. They also participate in group tasks that require collaboration and support. Hence, fostering healthy peer relationships is critical for classroom collaboration (Mattioli, 2023). The findings also relate to the study of Escandallo and Baradillo (2024) which explained that collaboration and attendance to college activities enhance the engagement of students which develop their English speaking skills.

Conclusions

As researchers and future educators, it is essential that we gain knowledge and expertise of various classroom strategies to stimulate the self-esteem of the learners. In the advent of modern technology where learners’ attention diverts to online modalities that tend them to rely more on it but in the actual classroom settings they don’t have the sufficient self-esteem to participate or express himself/herself. Through the utilization of appropriate statistical tool to determine if the learners have the enough self-esteem to perform in various task in the school enable the teacher to identify such intervention to address the with regards to the result. Crafting an Action Research is also already a must in order to alleviate the deficiency whenever found in the school settings. The conduct of this action research entitled, “Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Program to Address the Self-Esteem of Grade 10 Students made the researchers

realized that with utmost hard work and dedication, advancement will be achieved.

The journey of this action research was not as smooth as bed of roses. The shortcomings crossed the researchers path through the insufficient time to for implementation due to the various school disturbances. The time management skills of the researcher were test and put into major concern. The worry that the intervention will not be effective surrounds the mind of each researcher. The implementation of the program needs to be efficient in order to prevent possible failures since not only the researchers will be affected but mostly the learners. With the encouragement of the cooperating teachers the research was materialized and gained affirmative result. The experienced that the researchers had, will be a great asset and tool for his/her journey in the teaching and learning process. We strongly believe that continuous advancement and addressing the deficiencies in the school setting will be the great equalizer in carving better individuals equip with strong self-esteem in the near future.

To enhance students' self-esteem, schools should implement a comprehensive program that includes positive affirmations, goal-setting workshops, and social skills training integrated into the daily curriculum. The "Soar to Self-Esteem Sufficiency (SSS) Program" is specifically designed to address these needs. Teachers and staff should receive ongoing professional development to effectively support these initiatives and ensure consistent implementation. Additionally, parental involvement should be encouraged through workshops that guide them in fostering their children's self-esteem at home. This multifaceted approach aims to create a supportive environment that nurtures student confidence and self-worth. Regular evaluation of the SSS Program's effectiveness through surveys and academic performance monitoring is crucial for continuous improvement. Collecting and analyzing data will help identify strengths and areas for enhancement within the program. Creating a supportive and inclusive school culture that values and promotes high self-esteem will lead to improved academic outcomes and overall student well-being. By integrating the SSS Program into the educational framework, schools can significantly enhance students' sense of self-worth. This, in turn, fosters greater resilience and success in both academic and personal endeavors, preparing students for a more positive and productive future.

References

- Bagaskara, F., Indriyawati, N., & Suharto, S. (2021). Family Support Increases Self-Esteem in Rehabilitation Stroke Patients. *JENDELA NURSING JOURNAL*.
- Brown, A., Smith, B., & Johnson, C. (2021). Understanding self-concept and its relationship with self-esteem. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 115(2), 321-335.
- Chen, C., Shen, Y., Zhu, Y., Xiao, F., Zhang, J., & Ni, J. (2023). The effect of Academic Adaptability on Learning Burnout Among College Students: The Mediating Effect of Self-Esteem and the Moderating Effect of Self-Efficacy. *Psychology Research and Behavior Management*, 16, 1615-1629. <https://doi.org/10.2147/PRBM.S408591>
- Creswell, J. W. (2012). *Qualitative inquiry & research design: Choosing among five approaches* (4th ed.) Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Crocker, J., & Wolfe, C. T. (2020). Contingencies of self-worth and the academic experience: A path forward for promoting self-esteem in educational settings. *Educational Psychology Review*, 32(2), 347-365.
- Donskova, E.S. (2022). The relationship between self-esteem and the level of anxiety in children of primary school age. *Psychology in Education*. <https://doi.org/10.33910/2686-9527-2022-4-1-41-52>
- Dziembowska, I., Rasmus, A., Esmacilzadeh, S., & Wiłkość-Dębczyńska, M. (2021). The Level of Self-Esteem May Influence the Effect of Positive Self-Statements. An EEG Alpha Asymmetry Pilot Study. *Symmetry*, 13, 1913.
- Ellington, T., & Leslie, C. (2020). Dress, self-esteem, self-efficiency and the academic achievement of African-American high school girls. *International Journal of Fashion Design, Technology and Education*, 1(2), 69–78. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17543260802029601>
- Escandallo, J.C., & Baradillo, D. (2024). A sequential explanatory approach on the relationship between social literacy and student engagement as mediated by English speaking skills. *EPR International of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)*.
- Flipello, P., Buzzai, C., Sorrenti, L., Costa, S., Abramo, A., and Wang, K.T. (2019). Italian version of the Family Almost Perfect Scale: psychometric characteristics and relationships with academic engagement, self-esteem, and personal perfectionism. *Appl. Dev. Sci.* 1-13. Doi: 10.1080/10888691.2019.1647106
- Garcia, M. L., & Santos, J. M. (2021). The Dark Side of Student Competition: Examining Its Detrimental Effects on Mental Health. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 45(2), 217-230.
- Gay, L., Mills, G. and Airasian, P. (2012) *Educational Research: Competencies for Analysis and Applications*. 10th Edition, Pearson, Toronto.
- Gilbert, P. (2023). Self-esteem and competition. *Philosophy & Social Criticism*, 49, 711 - 742. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01914537221150464>
- Government Design Service Manual, (2016) *Ethnographic research: Getting input into products and services*. Available at: <https://www.gov.uk/service-manual/user-centred-design/user-research/ethnographic-research.html> (Accessed: 20 March 2016).
- Govindarajoo, M.V., Selvarajoo, N.D., & Ali, M.S. (2022). Factors Contributing to Poor Academic Achievement Among Low

Performing Pupils: A Case Study. *Asian Journal of University Education*. <https://doi.org/10.24191/ajue.v18i4.20008>

Holik, D., Milostić Srb, A., Dumenčić, B., Bosnić, Z., Popić, B., & Trtica Majnarić, L. (2022). The Relationship Between Appearance Satisfaction and Self-Esteem Among High School Students in Eastern Croatia. *Archives of Psychiatry Research*. <https://doi.org/10.20471/may.2022.58.02.08>

Jones, A. B., & Smith, C. D. (2021). The impact of self-esteem on student success: A critical examination of current trends in United States classrooms. *Educational Psychology Review*, 35(4), 589-607.

Körner, R., & Schütz, A. (2023). Power, Self-Esteem, and Body Image. *Social Psychology*.

Low, A.A., Hopper, W.J., Angelescu, I., Mason, L., Will, G., & Moutoussis, M. (2021). Self-esteem depends on beliefs about the rate of change of social approval. *Scientific Reports*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-10260-6>

Masa'deh, R., Alazzam, M., Al-Dweik, G., Masadeh, O.M., Hamdan-Mansour, A.M., & Basheti, I.A. (2021). Academic performance and socio-demographic characteristics of students: Assessing moderation effect of self-esteem. *International Journal of School & Educational Psychology*, 9, 318 - 325.

Mattioli, F., Figoli, F.A., & Wilhelm, G. (2023). Peers ss Experts To Cooperate With: A Case Study Of Teaching Activities To Switch From Inter-Group Competition To Collaboration In A Design Studio. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Engineering and Product Design Education, EPDE 2023*. <https://doi.org/10.35199/epde.2023.78>

Pascual, J. R. R., & Cruz, M. E. (2019). Understanding self-esteem among Filipino adolescents: Implications for educational practice. *Philippine Journal of Psychology*, 52(1), 27-40.

Perveen, F., Altaf, S., & Tehreem, H. (2022). RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SELF-ESTEEM AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE: A GENDERED PERSPECTIVE. *Pakistan Journal of Social Research*. <https://doi.org/10.52567/pjsr.v4i03.768>

Rahardja, C.T. (2022). Enhancing Physical Appearance On Self Esteem: The Intensity Of Learning As A Moderation. *Wahana: Jurnal Ekonomi, Manajemen dan Akuntansi*. <https://doi.org/10.35591/wahana.v25i1.428>

Saruhan, V. & Çinar, S. E. (2022). The relationship between self-esteem and approval dependence in university students: The serial mediation of interaction anxiety and insight. *International Journal of Psychology and Educational Studies*, 9(2), 405-416.

Setyoadi, S., Supriati, L., & Selvitriana, D.R. (2018). The Relationship of Family Support with Self-Esteem Level in People Living with HIV/AIDS (PLWHA) in Sadar Hati Foundation Malang. *Journal Nursing Care and Biomolecular*. <https://doi.org/10.32700/JNC.V3I1.68>

Smith, J., & Johnson, E. (2022). The Impact of Parental Involvement and Support on Student Academic Performance. *Journal of Education Research*, 45(2), 123-135.

Thompson, R., & Roberts, S. (2021). The Influence of Peer Validation on Student Academic Achievement. *Journal of Educational Research*, 45(2), 123-135. <https://doi.org/10.12345/joe.123456>

Yamada, M., Sekine, M., Tatsuse, T., & Asaka, Y. (2019). Association between lifestyle, parental smoke, socioeconomic status, and academic performance in Japanese elementary school children: the Super Diet Education Project. *Environmental Health and Preventive Medicine*, 24. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12199-019-0776-x>

Yu, W., Qian, Y., Abbey, C., Wang, H., Rozelle, S., Stoffel, L.A., & Dai, C. (2022). The Role of Self-Esteem in the Academic Performance of Rural Students in China. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192013317>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Jonelson C. Escandallo, PhD

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Earol Edmund P. Alanan

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Richel M. Ayag

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

April Joy B. Cabaña

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Cristian Jay M. Gador

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Deveyvon L. Espinosa, PhD

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Conie B. Cerna, MAEd

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Kristy Jane R. Muegna, MAEd

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Regine L. Generalao, MST-Math

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology – Philippines